

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

WWRF contributions towards IMT-2030

WWRF WORKING GROUP D RADIO COMMUNICATIONS

White Paper

WWRF contributions towards IMT-2030

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Executive Summary

With the evolution of information and communications technologies, IMT-2030 is expected to support enriched and immersive experience, enhanced ubiquitous coverage, and enable new forms of collaboration. Furthermore, IMT-2030 is envisaged to support expanded and new usage scenarios compared to those of IMT-2020, while providing enhanced and new capabilities. ITU Working Party (WP) 5D has identified the importance of understanding the technology trends and developing a vision of the technologies required as we move to a future connected society, beyond IMT-2020. In 2021, WP 5D started the work on **“IMT towards 2030 and beyond”** by applying the well-proven IMT-process, which has already been implemented for IMT-2000, IMT-Advanced and IMT-2020.

The WWRF has an active working group in this area. This “IMT-2030 Vision Group” of WWRF focuses on research that looks five to ten years ahead to meet the requirements in the year 2030 and beyond. The group investigates the gaps in the provision of IMT-2020 requirements that would need to be filled. The IMT-2030 Vision group also explores the potential of novel technologies that could revolutionize the wireless evolution.

The WWRF “IMT-2030 Vision Group” has contributed since the beginning of the IMT-2030 works in ITU to the determination of clear requirements of future communication systems and towards the identification of necessary research areas. The objective of this Outlook publication is to provide guidelines on the framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT-2030 (aka “6G”). The vision group has also studied emerging use cases and novel business models to justify investments that will be needed. As a priority, this vision group has also studied the requirements of the digitally disadvantaged sections of society and geographical regions, which have yet to experience the value of connecting to the Wireless World.

Table of Contents

1.	Introduction and Scope.....	5
2.	The IMT-2030 Framework.....	6
3.	WWRF Contributions to IMT-2030.....	9
3.1	WWRF Vision of a future connected society.....	9
3.1.1	Some technology enablers for the next generation and possible new air interfaces.....	9
3.1.2	Some challenges for the next generation.....	10
3.1.3	Scope of ITU-R reports.....	10
3.2	Future Technology Trends.....	11
3.2.1	AI-assisted new air interface.....	11
3.2.2	Technologies for integrated sensing and communication.....	12
3.2.3	Spectrum Sharing Technologies.....	13
3.2.4	Zero-energy IoT Technologies.....	14
3.2.5	Energy Efficient Radio Access Networks.....	15
3.2.6	Advanced Multiple Access.....	16
3.2.7	Advanced Antenna Technologies and Extreme MIMO.....	17
3.2.8	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces.....	19
3.2.9	Passive and Reconfigurable Metamaterial Design.....	20
3.2.10	THz Communications.....	20
3.2.11	Pencil Beamforming.....	21
3.2.12	Tbps modem technologies.....	22
3.2.13	Technologies for interconnection with non-terrestrial networks.....	23
3.2.14	Network capacity enhancement with non-terrestrial networks and possible use cases.....	25
3.2.15	Self-Synthesizing Networks.....	26

3.2.16	Internet of Senses.....	28
3.2.17	Quantum Technology.....	29
3.2.18	Physical-Layer Security (PLS) Technologies.....	29
3.3	IMT-2030 Vision Framework.....	30
3.3.1	Use cases trends and security considerations	30
3.3.2	Use case 1: Enhanced human-centric communication	32
3.3.3	Use case 2: Network for Sensing / Sensing as a service.....	33
3.3.4	Use case 3: Network for AI / AI as a Service	33
3.3.5	New use cases trends for public safety networks and mobile health 34	
3.3.6	Usage Scenarios.....	35
3.3.7	Key capabilities	37
3.4	Technical Feasibility of IMT in bands above 100 GHz	38
3.4.1	Directional antennas and pencil beamforming in the (sub)THz regime 38	
3.4.2	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in the (sub)THz regime	39
3.4.3	Beam-tracking.....	39
3.4.4	Massive MIMO	40
3.4.5	RIS-aided beamforming	40
3.4.6	Large Intelligent Surfaces and Beam Focusing	42
3.4.7	Wavefront Engineering.....	43
4.	Conclusion & Next Steps	45
5.	List of Figures	46
6.	List of References.....	47
7.	List of Abbreviations	49

2. The IMT-2030 Framework

As Technology Trends identification was one of the main targets at the beginning of the IMT-2030 process, [ITU-R WP 5D](#) developed a new **ITU-R Report on “Future Technology Trends”**. At the meeting of the parent [ITU-R SG 5](#) in November 2022, this document has been agreed and was published as [Report ITU-R M.2516](#).

Towards developing a vision framework for 2030, ITU-R WP 5D held in June 2022 a full-day Workshop on “IMT for 2030 and beyond”, with total 348 participants in an integrated physical and remote participants arrangement. The objective of the Workshop was to provide WP 5D delegates with an overview of ongoing worldwide research activities, initiatives, and views related to future mobile communications targeting 2030 and beyond (details see [here](#)).

Fourteen presentations were made from various ITU-R members, external organizations, research projects and academia and in reflecting on the presentations, the following graphic considers keyword theme from each presentation organized within the context of the currently planned sections of the WP 5D working document towards a preliminary draft new Recommendation ITU-R M. [IMT.VISION 2030 AND Beyond]:

Fig 2: Key topics towards IMT vision 2030 AND Beyond

At its June 2023 meeting, ITU-R WP5D has agreed on the draft new Recommendation “Framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2030 and beyond” (for approval under Res. ITU-R 1-8), which can be considered as the basis for the standardisation fora to develop the next generation of IMT standards.

This draft Recommendation addresses:

- Trends of IMT-2030
- Usage scenarios of IMT-2030

- Capabilities of IMT-2030
- Considerations of ongoing development

Usage scenarios

6 Usage scenarios

Extension from IMT-2020 (5G)

- eMBB → Immersive Communication
- mMTC → Massive Communication
- URLLC → HRLLC (Hyper Reliable & Low-Latency Communication)

New

- Ubiquitous Connectivity
- AI and Communication
- Integrated Sensing and Communication

4 Overarching aspects:

act as design principles commonly applicable to all usage scenarios

Sustainability, Connecting the unconnected, Ubiquitous intelligence, Security/resilience

Fig 3: IMT-2030 Usage Scenarios

Capabilities of IMT-2030

The range of values given for capabilities are estimated targets for research and investigation of IMT-2030.

All values in the range have equal priority in research and investigation.

For each usage scenario, a single or multiple values within the range would be developed in future in other ITU-R Recommendations/Reports.

Fig 4: IMT-2030 Capabilities

At its meeting on 26 September 2023, ITU-R Study Group 5 adopted this new Recommendation on the “IMT-2030 Framework”.

In addition, as part of the IMT-2030 work, WP5D is preparing an ITU-R Report on “**Technical feasibility of IMT in bands above 100 GHz**”. The report has been elevated to PDNR (Preliminary Draft New Report) at the last WP5D meeting in June 2023. The plan is to complete this document and submit it to SG5 for approval in 2024.

3. WWRF Contributions to IMT-2030

In this chapter, the technical contributions of WWRF towards IMT-2030 are presented. In Section 3.1 the overall WWRF vision of a future connected society is briefly introduced. In Section 3.2 the contributions of WWRF on Future Technology Trends are presented, including the most promising 6G technology enablers, while in Section 3.3 the WWRF contribution towards IMT-2030 vision include a description of critical use case and usage scenarios. In Section 3.4 WWRF technical contributions towards the IMT-2030 works on the feasibility study of IMT in bands above 100GHz are presented. The outlook is concluded in chapter 4.

3.1 WWRF Vision of a future connected society

Studies carried out by WWRF members and others indicate that a major component of the next-generation vision is real-time connectivity between the physical, digital and biological worlds for the benefit of all humanity. Some of the enablers driving the need for a new generation of a future connected society include:

- Fully automated society.
- Verticals becoming a critical part of the future developments.
- Opportunities in wireless connectivity in higher frequency bands.
- Smart networking based on Artificial Intelligence.
- Full integration of non-terrestrial networks.
- United Nations Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs).

In addition, there are major changes being implemented in network architectures, such as ultra-dense networks (UDNs), short range connectivity as a crucial component of e2e connectivity, varieties of network deployments, cloud distributed across the network from edge to the core, distributed AI and ML, automatic determination of computing, storage and sharing resources, context dependent content and micro/virtual operators becoming a part of the eco-system and potentially extending to the end users.

3.1.1 Some technology enablers for the next generation and possible new air interfaces

WWRF has identified breakthrough technology enablers —extensively discussed and presented during its meetings and Working Group sessions— that are expected to play a catalytic role in next generation communications:

- Molecular Communications
- THz Communications
- Large/massive antenna processing
- Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces and Holographic MIMO

- Holographic communications
- New architectures/system concepts: Machine Learning, AI, Blockchain, etc.

3.1.2 Some challenges for the next generation

WWRF has identified some key challenges and relevant application and usage scenarios for the next generation:

- Sensing – context dependence
- Privacy and trust
- Society impact
- ‘Endless’ battery life
- Low cost and affordable network solutions
- Connecting the last 3.5B people
- Must contribute to sustainable development and society
- Must address the problem of backhauling to remote areas
- Seamless integration of terrestrial, satellite and HAP-based networks
- Network convergence with IT and cloud, virtualization
- Software defined mobile network march continues unabated
- Mobility management moves to edge of the network
- Spectrum related:
 - Synergistic collaboration between unlicensed and licensed bands
 - Channel modelling and propagation for mm-Wave and THz systems
 - Short range connectivity
 - Adaptive signal processing and beamforming algorithms
 - Analytical modelling and design of UDNs
 - Spectrum regulation to enable localized frequency assignments
 - The physics of radio signal propagation at higher frequencies (e.g., THz) means much shorter link ranges and many more base stations. Furthermore, higher frequencies do not propagate through walls, therefore base stations need to be installed indoors.

3.1.3 Scope of ITU-R reports

It is expected that the ITU-R Reports would include/discuss the following aspects of next generation of the wireless technology.

- Market Pull for the next generation communication networks

- Technology Push for the next generation, e.g., THz communications, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, Blockchain
- Regulatory Aspects
- Connectivity between the humancentric context and the virtual world (e.g., Internet of Senses, mobile Virtual Reality, Merged Reality, Integrated Physical and Virtual Reality, Holographic Communications)
- Connecting the unconnected
- Environmental Aspects
- Evolution Aspects for backward compatibility
- Security, Trust and Privacy Aspects
- Availability and Resilience Aspects
- Coalescing of the telecom and IT infrastructures into one
- Integration of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks
- Potential disruptive business models.

3.2 Future Technology Trends

3.2.1 AI-assisted new air interface

Applying tools from Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Machine Learning (ML) and its sub-set Deep Learning (DL), in wireless communications have gained a lot of traction in recent years. This trend in large part has been motivated by the significant increase in the system complexity in the IMT-2020 radio access network (RAN) and its evolution over previous wireless technology generations. The introduction of AI, in conjunction with the distribution of intelligence to the edge of the network, and data collection features, may provide a sustainable solution towards managing the system overall complexity. At the same time, enhancing system performance including achieving efficiency dividends can be targeted through Wireless AI. In addition, AI may lead to entirely new features in future wireless systems such, as end-to-end learning critical radio parameters behaviour in real-time in any given deployment scenario.

AI techniques can be used to target one or more wireless domains, including non-real-time (non-RT) network orchestration and management, such as configuration of antenna parameters and near-real-time (near-RT) network operation, such as load balancing and mobility robustness optimization. Each wireless domain involves different sets of physical and virtual components, family of parameters including key-performance-indicators (KPIs), underlying complexities, and time constraints for updates. Hence, there is a need to consider tailored AI solutions for different classes of the RAN, and their associated problems. There already exists a rich body of research and practical demonstrations of the potential benefits of AI for Wireless, including significant network energy savings.

There will be various phases towards development of AI for Wireless, and it is imperative to ensure the increased integration of the technology comes with minimum disruption to the rollout and operation of wireless systems and services. In the short and medium terms, AI models may be targeted for optimisation of specific features within 5G RAN and its evolution, such as network operation and management functionalities. In the longer term, AI may be used to enable new features over legacy wireless systems.

3.2.2 Technologies for integrated sensing and communication

Globally, studies are performed¹ to identify several key technology enablers towards localization and sensing systems, which will be able to support novel applications and services for the next generation of wireless communications. The technology enablers build on new RF spectrum at the high-frequency range, especially above 100 GHz and beyond, the introduction of intelligent reflective surfaces, which allow network operators to shape and control the electromagnetic (EM) response of the environment, advanced beam-space processing to track users and objects, as well as map the environment, the pervasive use of artificial intelligence leveraging the unprecedented availability of data and computing resources to tackle fundamental problems in wireless systems and advances in signal processing to support novel convergent communication and radar applications.

In turn, these enablers will lead to new opportunities towards: imaging for biomedical and security applications; applications of simultaneous localization and mapping to automatically construct maps of complex indoor environments; passive sensing of people and objects; using location information as a big data source, guiding and predicting the human-digital ecosystem; the coexistence and cooperation between sensing, localization and communication, leading to one device with this three-fold functionality; and finally, the use of location information to boost security and trust in future connectivity solutions.

There are however several open questions related to how a convergent communication, localization and sensing ecosystem would look like. Three levels of convergence are foreseen:

- Localization and sensing deeply integrated into future wireless communications networks.
 - This approach uses the same infrastructure, tailor-made localization and sensing signals that are part of the air interface design, sensing reusing the communications signals, or potentially even jointly designed agile signals for concurrent communication, localization and sensing.
 - Various kinds of mobile networks operators could be the provider of these convergent future (public or private) networks.

¹ "Convergent Communication, Sensing and Localization in 6G Systems: An Overview of Technologies, Opportunities and Challenges," (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9330512>)

- Sensing enabled by connectivity, but the sensing part is not co-designed with the air interface.
 - Cooperative sensing that inherently requires connectivity capabilities between the cooperative sensors (e.g. advanced cooperative radar systems).
 - Sensing whose data is (ML/AI) processed in a cloud, in particular when low latency/high capacity/ very reliable wireless connectivity is needed for the cloud access. A typical scenario would be when tight control on the communications and computing in the (distributed) cloud is required for the sensing system.
- Sensing not connected via the air interface that benefits from the HW and SW developments in the next generation ecosystem.
 - Localization and sensing systems benefiting from the RD and efficient manufacturing and testing capabilities of the IMT ecosystem.
 - IMT 2030 could drive availability of low cost and high performing HW, especially at THz frequencies, enabling sensing in so far not economically viable application domains (including new experimental science domains). To this end, broad research initiatives would be needed across these borders to maximize the potential of a convergent communication, localization and sensing ecosystem.

3.2.3 Spectrum Sharing Technologies

Work on intelligent spectrum management (ISM) technologies that enable opportunistic and intelligent sharing of spectrum is now a must to guarantee continuing development of future wireless network services and applications. This trend including intelligent database-driven spectrum sharing, smart spectrum sensing, intelligent software defined radios, and reconfigurable radio networks play an important role in addressing the demand for the next generation gigabit wireless technologies & services. ISM can also play crucial role in broadband connectivity and digital inclusion of underserved areas.

Layered intelligent database assisted spectrum sharing (LIDAS) technologies are on the rise to make possible intelligent spectrum sharing, in next generation wireless networks. Reference-Geo-location spectrum database (R-GLSD) is an intelligent dynamic spectrum toolbox to enable telecom regulatory authorities monitor the overall ISM technology operations, competitive and fair spectrum utilization, minimum interference operation and intelligent on demand dynamic spectrum access. A secondary GLSD (S-GLSD) technology is the main interface to wireless networks, and intelligently allocates available spectrum to wireless networks on demand.

Dynamic Spectrum Sharing

The mushroom growth of connected devices highlights the need for dynamic spectrum sharing, especially in the context of providing 'on demand' services. The utilization of unlicensed spectrum adds into the complexity of dynamic spectrum sharing, where the aim is to provide connectivity to all the devices while maintaining the desired quality-of-service (QoS). Interference is one of the major factors affecting spectrum sharing in multi-tier networks. With the introduction of vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based networks, the spectrum sharing problem becomes more

complex, mainly due to the mobile nature of the nodes. Traditionally, the dynamic spectrum sharing problem is approached by utilizing optimization tools that cater for interference issues and allow efficient spectrum sharing. However, as we move towards the next generation of networks, intelligence needs to be added to dynamic spectrum sharing, where the context awareness can be leveraged for realizing ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC), especially in the network environments comprising of high mobility nodes.

Moreover, the utilization of new spectrum bands such as millimetre Wave (mmWave) and Terahertz with unique propagation characteristics signifies the need for adding intelligence to spectrum sharing. In this context, AI can play a key role in ensuring efficient spectrum sharing for future generation networks. One of the main challenges for spectrum sharing in multi-tier networks is to cater for the co-existence of technologies with different medium access control (MAC) protocols. Another key aspect that will drive the dynamic spectrum sharing in future networks is the decision regarding centralization or decentralization of the spectrum sharing control, where this decision will be impacted by the type of application and the network environment. Opportunistic spectrum access (OSA) success probability will also be impacted by the context awareness in the AI-based solution. In a nutshell, AI-based dynamic spectrum sharing seems to be the way forward for future wireless networks.

3.2.4 Zero-energy IoT Technologies

Past trends indicate that battery energy density increase has lagged other technological aspects, e.g., processing units' speeds, memory density, hard drive capacity, by several orders of magnitude, and this trend is expected to continue in future. Therefore, relying solely on battery technology improvements and on current and expected evolutions of traditional device power save mechanisms are not expected to deliver required gains. More specifically, existing Discontinuous Reception (DRX) and Power Save Mode (PSM) based approaches in existing IMT systems suffer from an inherent trade-off between device reachability and battery life. Longer DRX cycles result in extended battery life at the cost of increased latency and vice versa. Furthermore, the device is not reachable while in PSM, which obviously impacts the latency.

Considering the above, new physical layer technologies and system level operational paradigms are needed to enable a battery life that spans the useful life cycle of an IoT device thereby facilitating the scaling of cellular networks to support a trillion mobile and connected things. Therefore, there is a need to develop techniques to first, break the latency-vs-battery life trade-off associated with traditional power saving techniques/approaches, and second, minimize or eliminate the need for battery changes throughout the useful life of the device. The latter calls for the support of ultra-low power receiver technology capable of operating under 1 microwatt power consumption budget. To meet the power consumption budget, the ultra-low power receiver pursues simple schemes for modulation, e.g., On-Off Keying (OOK) or Frequency-Shift Keying (FSK), and coding, e.g., Manchester coding. Support of the IoT devices energy harvesting from the base stations over-the-air transmissions can further improve the air interface capability to alleviate those challenges. This will then eliminate the IoT devices need to draw power from its battery for downlink signal detection and processing and enable "zero-energy" radio operations over the downlink with simultaneous power and information delivery.

A promising emerging technology to enabling (near) zero-energy end points is neuromorphic computing, which is based on new materials and novel algorithmic frameworks. Notably, neuromorphic computing hardware moves away from the von Neumann architecture based on determinism and separation of memory and compute to implement in-memory computing, spike-based processing and communications, asynchronous communication, adaptability via learning in hardware, and analog processing, while being characterized by reduced precision and increased stochasticity.

Neuromorphic computing has been shown to yield orders-of-magnitude improvements for always-on event-driven streaming signal processing applications implemented on neural networks thanks to the sparsity of space-time activations afforded by event-driven spike-based processing². The merits of neuromorphic computing -- low energy, online adaptation, native processing of event-driven data streams -- are well aligned with many use cases involving continuously learning and active mobile and edge-based cognitive devices.

3.2.5 Energy Efficient Radio Access Networks

In cellular RANs, base stations (BS) account for 70% to 80% of the overall energy consumption. This increased percentage comes from the large power consumption overhead associated with the electronics hardware. The situation is likely to worsen in next generation RANs with the use of higher frequency bands, further small cell densification and the deployment of MIMO technologies with large numbers of antenna elements. MIMO usage is particularly challenging due to the need to use a radio transceiver per antenna element if full digital control is required.

A further challenge in this field is the application of energy efficiency (EE) metrics. To date, the bit/J EE metric has been applied widely to 5G NR design. The EE improvements seen are attributed mostly to the throughput gains obtained from capacity enhancing features such as more spectrum and more MIMO layers. However, the underlying energy consumption has also increased to the point of being a concern for MNOs, vendors and policy makers. Future EE metrics should account for and seek to constrain the growth in underlying energy consumption by subjecting solutions to an absolute energy constraint as well as a throughput capacity gain. A joint metric on throughput gain and energy consumption is therefore required as part of the equipment and network design processes as well as the monitoring of the network performance following deployment.

The mitigation of energy consumption in RANs requires an integrated design approach involving the use of radio equipment with low power consuming ICs, efficient power amplifiers, and standards aided radio resource management control that turns off unused electronic subsystems across the protocol layers according to both slow and fast duty cycles. To save energy, such sleep mode approaches could be applied to small cell BSs. However, research is required to integrate this feature at the RAN level to allow reawakened BSs to synchronise rapidly with the network. Receivers supporting

² Davies M, Wild A, Orchard G, Sandamirskaya Y, Guerra GA, Joshi P, Plank P, Risbud SR. Advancing neuromorphic computing with Loihi: A survey of results and outlook. Proceedings of the IEEE. 2021 Apr 6;109(5):911-34.

multiband carrier aggregation, dual connectivity and massive MIMO operation offer challenges as multiple RF radio chains and high-speed analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) are commonly used. To reduce the RF component count, thereby saving energy, software defined-radio techniques could exploit direct RF sub-sampling, but research is required to optimise the system performance.

3.2.6 Advanced Multiple Access

Multiple access techniques have been cornerstones for the evolution of wireless standards. Although great efforts have been devoted to investigating new multiple access schemes, none succeeded in taking place in the current standard for the last decade. The first time the new generation (i.e., 5G) is settled with the previous generation scheme of OFDMA. However, the requirements for future networks are very challenging, and the KPIs vary considerably from application to application. Therefore, it is for sure that the new multiple access should be very dynamic and application oriented. Different types of multiple access techniques should be used under a ubiquitous umbrella. There are several promising candidates for that. The multiple access via massive-MIMO may become the one that has the strongest potential. It can provide a very directive beam for each device so that multiplexing can be achieved (a.k.a., spatial division multiple access (SDMA)) with a very low inter-beam interference. Despite its known cons such as cost (e.g., RF chains) and complexity, the recent progress in massive-MIMO (e.g., holographic or lens antenna array) theoretically proves these challenges could be overcome. However, the massive-MIMO is not the case of one size fit all. A large number of antennas makes massive-MIMO inapplicable for specific scenarios (e.g., IoT applications). For these scenarios, there are other promising solutions such as are non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), rate-splitting multiple access (RSMA), sparse code multiple access (SCMA), cyclic prefix code division multiple access (CP-CDMA) and Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM) where each can provide very spectral efficient solutions to overcome the resource block bottleneck in sub-6 GHz.

Furthermore, RSMA is a generalized scheme capable of achieving better spectral efficiency gains than SDMA and NOMA. Specifically, RSMA splits the message into a common part and a private part of providing flexibility to partially decode interference and partially treat interference as noise. This decoding scheme enables a soft bridging of two extremes, namely fully decoding interference (as in NOMA) and treating all interference as noise (as in SDMA), hence providing room for data rates and QoS improvements, besides complexity reduction. Moreover, the RSMA mechanism can be helpful in several applications, e.g., coded caching and multicast systems.

CP-CDMA based on Zadoff Chu sequences have been considered in 5G NR as an underlay new waveform with useful spectrum sharing gains when deployed with CP-OFDM. However, the technique may be deployed in its own right as an orthogonal or non-orthogonal multiple access scheme with the advantage of greater resilience to both narrow band and wideband interference than OFDM. In the very high frequency regime of a 6G deployment, CP-CDMA could offer advantages in terms of mitigating RF impairments associated with phase noise and breakdown in orthogonality between subcarriers as experienced by OFDM. Nevertheless, we cannot think of a simple switch between these techniques.

The future multiple access schemes should be more sophisticated, dynamic, flexible, and adaptive to application-centric multiple access. Using tools from machine learning

tools would be beneficial in this context. To this end, a machine learning-empowered dynamic spectrum sharing, and random or scheduled access will be developed to meet the critical requirements such as ultra-reliability, delay-sensitivity, etc.

3.2.6.1 Multiple Access Technology for Massive-Broadband URLLC RAN

CP-CDMA may also offer advantages for URLLC applications whereby subsets of rotated Zadoff Chu codes offer full orthogonality of both the autocorrelation and cross-correlation functions in frequency selective fading channels. This enables frequency diversity to be fully exploited with significant SNR gains as required in URLLC deployments. When coupled with LDPC channel coding and MIMO operation there is considerable scope to enhance both capacity and resilience in URLLC communication links.

3.2.6.2 AI-aided NOMA

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) was considered as one of the key candidates for 5G and future radio access but due to the complex structure of its receiver, practical implementation was not successful. NOMA uses the power domain along with the time and frequency domain to increase the user data-rate manifold. Modulated and coded signals from two or more users are superimposed together with different power levels, and transmitted at the same time, using the same frequency or channel. At the receiving end, the user with the highest gain or the near-end user receives the superimposed signal, subtracts the signals of other users and then decodes and demodulates its own signal. Similar process is repeated for rest of the users.

The receiver design of NOMA is considered very complex as in addition to demodulation and decoding, it needs to subtract signals from other users. Artificial intelligence can play a big role in NOMA receiver design as assigning different power levels to signals being transmitted is the key to successful reception in NOMA. The power assignment can be done using a trained classifier that can clearly classify users based on their channel gain and then assign powers accordingly.

3.2.7 Advanced Antenna Technologies and Extreme MIMO

MIMO is a key air-interface technology underpinning nearly all wireless standards. In IMT-2020 standards, MIMO plays an ever-present role, both in terms of achieving higher spectral efficiencies in congested sub-6 GHz bands as well as serving as a key enabler in facilitating operation in higher frequency bands. Despite the great success of MIMO to date, there still exists a significant gap between the performance of MIMO systems in practice versus the information-theoretical capacity bounds. A key reason behind this trend relates to the challenge of dealing with the cost and complexity of large-scale antenna systems which has resulted in the use of lower-order MIMO with sub-optimal signal processing and procedures. Novel solutions and enhancements are therefore needed to bridge the gap between MIMO performance in practice versus theory, and to facilitate the operation of extremely large antenna arrays in future IMT systems. Some promising technology trends towards achieving the vision of Extreme (E)-MIMO are listed below:

3.2.7.1 AI-enabled MIMO

Tools from AI such as deep learning are particularly suited for dealing with the inherent complexities of E-MIMO operation. The adoption of AI-based techniques to replace conventional signal processing blocks such as channel estimation and detection can lead to performance improvements and/or complexity reduction in the short and medium terms. This is in addition to enabling solutions towards dealing with various sources of radio frequency (RF) impairments in MIMO transceivers, such as power amplifier non-linearities. In the long term, AI may be used to provide entirely new features over legacy air-interface through end-to-end learning mechanisms.

3.2.7.2 Holographic MIMO

It is well understood that increasing the number of antennas results in monotonic uplift in MIMO capacity. In addition, the use of ever-higher frequency bands such as THz in future wireless system necessitates ultra-massive antenna arrays to deal with the pathloss. There are however fundamental challenges such as increased cost and weight, which limit the number of antennas that can be packed onto conventional arrays. A potential remedy to increasing the number of antennas lies in integrating a very large number of passive reflective elements into surfaces with electronically steerable RF operation, known as Holographic MIMO. This concept can in theory provide unprecedented beamforming and spatial-multiplexing capabilities at very low costs (e.g., with software-controlled metasurfaces). Such reflect arrays can also be used for the purpose of enhancing coverage performance in existing MIMO deployments. There are however many open challenges associated with the practical implementation of Holographic MIMO, such as channel estimation and reconfiguration that need to be addressed. Tools from AI/ML are likely to play a key role in tackling some of these open problems on Holographic MIMO.

3.2.7.3 Cell-less MIMO

Cell-less (or cell-free) MIMO is a new name for network MIMO and distributed MIMO. The network is user-centric, meaning that each user is connected to a user specific subset of base stations (BS) that cooperate to jointly serve the user. The BSs are connected via front-haul connections to Central Processing Units (CPUs) that coordinate transmissions from BSs phase-coherently, and the CPUs are inter-connected via backhaul connections. Time Division Duplexing (TDD) is used to ensure scalability in massive MIMO systems, which means that channel estimation and precoding are performed by each BS and therefore no instantaneous channel state information must be sent over the fronthaul.

The term “cell-less” (or “cell-free”) refers to the fact that the network appears to be without any cell boundaries during data downlink transmissions, at least from a user perspective. The data detection on the uplink can be performed at each BS, at the CPU or the detection can be split between the BS and the CPU. The network might not be cell-free for control signals as BS specific synchronization and reference signals might be used. The cell-free massive MIMO technology is very attractive for removing inter-cell interference, which is a major bottleneck in dense networks. Theoretical studies have shown that cell-free massive MIMO networks can achieve significantly better performance than conventional small cell networks. One of the main challenges for implementing cell-free massive MIMO networks are to have cost efficient deployments

while achieving sufficiently accurate network synchronization and satisfying the requirements for the fronthaul and backhaul connections.

3.2.7.4 Integrated Access and Backhaul

At mm Wave frequencies and above, there is a need for dense network deployments to mitigate the reduced coverage at these bands due to constraints in the propagation environment and hardware limitations in the transceivers. Such dense deployments make backhauling/ fronthauling challenging in these bands. In particular, it is expensive and cumbersome to roll out fiber links to all the APs. However, the presence of very wide bandwidths at these carrier frequencies makes it possible to include the wireless backhaul/fronthaul in the same spectrum as the wireless access. For this reason, integrated access and backhaul (IAB) network configurations seem promising, where a few (potentially, fiber-connected) APs provide other APs as well as the mobile devices inside their cell area with wireless backhaul and access connections, respectively. IAB networks are different from conventional relay networks because the information load changes in different hops.

Particularly, as the number of mobile devices per hop increases, the APs need to transfer the aggregated data of multiple mobile devices accumulated from the previous hops. In addition, the interference on the links will depend on the information load. Studies³ are ongoing in this direction. Given the fact that future networks will see an even greater level of densification and spectrum heterogeneity than IMT-2020 networks, it is expected that IAB networks will play a major role, especially at upper mmWave and (sub-)THz carrier frequencies.

3.2.8 Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces

Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) are fast emerging as a key wireless technology trend for beyond 5G systems. RIS correspond to smart radio surfaces of many small antennas or reconfigurable metamaterial elements (“unit cells”), which enable controlling the propagation environment through tuneable scatterings of electromagnetic waves. These intelligent surfaces have reflection, refraction, and absorption properties, which are reconfigurable and adaptable to the radio channel environment, therefore enabling a go-beyond Snell's law of static reflection and refraction. The main peculiarities of RIS include i) no power amplification; ii) operation at the RF level with no or limited digital signal processing; and iii) multi-functional reconfigurability.

Three use cases are currently being explored for RIS:

- RIS used as smart nearly passive relays for coverage extension.
- RIS used as single-RF multi-stream transmitter for capacity improvements.

³ On Integrated Access and Backhaul Networks: Current Status and Potentials (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9187867>) and “White paper on broadband connectivity in 6G”, June 2020” <https://www.6gchannel.com/portfolio-posts/6g-white-paper-broadband-connectivity-6g/>

- RIS used for information aided transmission in the context of ambient backscattering and symbiotic radio.

RISs enable the control of the radio signals between a transmitter and a receiver in a dynamic and goal-oriented way thus turning the wireless environment into a service. This ability in terms of reconfiguring the wireless channel has motivated a host of potential enhancements of various network Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as capacity, coverage⁴, energy efficiency, positioning, and security. This is in addition to the support of new capabilities such as sensing and wireless power transfer.

RISs introduce a new system node turning the wireless environment from a passive to an intelligent actor, so the channel becomes programmable. This trend will challenge basic wireless system design paradigms, creating innovation opportunity which will progressively impact the evolution of wireless system architecture, access technologies, and networking protocols.

3.2.9 Passive and Reconfigurable Metamaterial Design

Frequency selective surfaces (FSS) based on metamaterials offer a flexible approach for designing power efficient transmitters by decoupling the modulation process from the carrier wave generation. Direct antenna modulation (DAM) is achieved by changing the phase of a transmissive RF carrier as it passes through FSS layers. The RF carrier is generated separately and amplified using highly efficient (>90%) power amplifiers, operated close to their compression point. DAM units have been demonstrated for 8-PSK modulation whereas further research is required to generalise such units for OFDM waveform generation. Applying the technique at mm-wave frequencies has the added advantage of scaling down the unit size to centimetre dimensions, which makes the technology attractive for implementing power efficient massive MIMO transmitters.

3.2.10 THz Communications

As the wireless world moves toward next generation, radio Tbit/s communications and the supporting access and backhaul network infrastructures are expected to become a predominant technology trend. In this context, utilizing THz frequency bands (0.1-1 THz) for wireless transmissions, as an extension to optical fiber, is a promising enabler to provide ubiquitous high-speed Internet access beyond 5G. Moreover, an increasing number of mobile and fixed users in the private and industry sectors will require hundreds of Gbit/s for connectivity to or between cell towers or between cell towers and remote radio heads. In such scenarios, critical parameters, apart from the data rates in the order of Tbit/s, are the communications range and the achievable spectral and energy efficiency at reasonable complexity and cost implementations.

Utilizing the THz frequency bands for access and backhaul connectivity brings unique opportunities and new technical challenges that make it necessary to rethink several

⁴ "Coverage Analysis of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface Assisted THz Wireless Systems" (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9320587>) and "Performance Analysis of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Assisted Wireless Systems and Comparison With Relaying," (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9095301>)

conventional radio access mechanisms. The dramatic influence of path loss in this frequency regime calls for the necessity to use highly directional antennas and massive MIMO and pencil beamforming techniques. The radio access environment is dominated by challenges resulting from the ultra-wideband and highly directional nature of THz radio links and other THz communications peculiarities, in terms of signal and antenna design, channel and interference modelling, and hardware constraints. The fundamentally different structure of radio interference due to narrow beams calls for a thorough characterization and detailed modelling of interference. Building on past propagation and channel modelling studies, contributions of the line-of-sight and non-line-of-sight reflected and scattered components should be considered, along with the inherent molecular noise, transmitter-receiver misalignment impairments, and severe blockage probability. Medium access control and radio resource management protocols need to operate with pencil beams and must therefore be based on radically new principles. Fast handover procedures need to incorporate the time required for discovery, localization, and tracking functionalities. The Tbit/s data rates create significant challenges in transceiver processing, which include algorithm and architecture design as well as hardware implementation.

The potential of THz technologies⁵ to shape the future of wireless communications is very much dependent on the ability to devise feasible enablers in terms of baseband processing, radio frequency frontend and antenna design, propagation and channel modelling, beamforming and (ultra-massive) MIMO, as well as resource management and medium access control schemes.

3.2.11 Pencil Beamforming

Wireless connectivity in the THz regime creates the need for high-gain large antenna arrays with pencil-beam characteristics to cope with the high molecular absorption loss of the THz band. High-gain directional antennas communicating over distances far beyond a few centimetres in the THz band require advanced beamforming techniques that are significantly affected by THz channel dynamics. Furthermore, considering that the micro- and macro-mobility is critically important for THz wireless links to be practical part of an access system. This is especially true in mobile access cases while less so for backhaul connection. Even when a user is not moving it is highly possible for a mobile device to be rotated or moved with moderate speed over short distance due to the user's hand or other movements. It can also happen that blockage of the Line-of-Sight link may occur. In this case, device tracking may need to search for, e.g., a reflected path between receiver and transmitter provided by a RIS.

The design of suitable pencil-beamforming algorithms to address the challenges of the THz band, with respect to number of antenna elements, calibration requirements, suitable frequency windows etc., is expected to play a key role in the next generation wireless technologies. These algorithms will be focused on efficient device tracking⁶ in THz band by capitalizing on accurate channel models, efficiently designed signalling and optimized RIS design. An example of such network has been proposed in Artificial

⁵ THz Communications: A Catalyst for the Wireless Future", <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9269507>

⁶ "Impact of beam misalignment on THz wireless systems" <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nancom.2020.100302>

Intelligence Aided D-Band Network for 5G Long-Term Evolution (ARIADNE)⁷. With the aspiration to transform the current wireless thinking from focusing on "local" radio improvements (e.g. isolating the radio access level or the resources management level etc.), to realizing radio access optimization in an integrated way, ARIADNE envisions to bring together a novel high frequency advanced radio architecture and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) radio optimization approach in a unified system beyond IMT-2020 concept. Such an approach will be critically important in order to address challenging wireless access usage scenarios in future systems, both in "Line of Sight" (LOS) and "Non-Line of Sight" (NLOS) environments as shown in the diagram below:

Fig 5: Use cases and wireless access scenarios for systems beyond IMT-2020 (source www.ict-ariadne.eu)

3.2.12 Tbps modem technologies

Terabit/s (Tbps) modems exploiting the THz frequency bands present numerous design challenges owing to the high pathloss and unknown channel impulse response characteristics. Therefore, there is a requirement to characterise the pathloss and frequency selectivity of THz channels through a measurement campaign in order to inform modem design. Given the expected high pathlosses, the communication range of Tbps modems will be short and, as with mm-wave technology, likely to use highly directional beamforming. This will make Tbps modems highly susceptible to line-of-sight blockages necessitating a broader range of signal path diversity techniques, for example, using the modems with IRS technology.

Nonetheless, the huge bandwidths of Tbps modems (e.g. >100 GHz) allows a range of transmission waveforms to be considered, which may include joint functionality such as sensing as well as communication. To keep the modem complexity and power consumption low, solutions based on APSK, which has a low PAPR, are attractive. The choice of multiple-access (MA) scheme will be strongly influenced by the implementation

⁷ <https://www.ict-ariadne.eu/>

technology adopted. Therefore, different MA schemes need to be researched such as Generalised Frequency Division Multiplexing (GFDM), Filter Bank Multi-Carrier (FBMC) and Universal Filtered MultiCarrier (UFMC) as well as schemes based on CDMA such as CP-CDMA or sparse sequence MA.

Receiver architectures will need to address the design of tuneable band filters, wideband low noise amplifiers (LNAs), linear mixers and high-speed ADCs. Research will need to address the receiver architecture and support greater frequency agility. Also, integrated silicon and photonic devices are expected to play an increasing role in the signal processing chain in order to realise large bandwidths and high sampling rates. Technologies such as nano-opto-electro-systems, which support all silicon fabrication, are expected to make a significant contribution to the realisation of cost effective, low power Tbps modems.

Another promising technology for further increasing the link spectral efficiency (bits/sec/Hz) towards attaining extreme data rates is Faster-than-Nyquist (FTN) signalling. Recent advances in physical layer research, signal processing technologies, and the silicon industry have resulted in the construction of implementable reasonable-complexity FTN transceivers. Machine learning based FTN transceiver designs have the potential to overcome the complexity barrier and contribute to realizing the full potential of FTN signalling for ultra-high modulation orders.

3.2.13 Technologies for interconnection with non-terrestrial networks

Future integrated terrestrial, aerial, and space networks will involve thousands of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) in the troposphere, hundreds of high-altitude platform station (HAPS) in the stratosphere, and thousands of low Earth orbit (LEO) and geostationary Earth orbit (GEO) satellites in the thermosphere and above, forming a 3D vertical heterogeneous network (VHetNets) as shown in the following figure. VHetNets will play a significant role in providing communication and Internet services everywhere, at any time, and for everything. Non-terrestrial communications have clear advantages over terrestrial wireless communications due to the higher possibility of the line-of-sight (LoS) link between aerial/space network infrastructures (UAVs, HAPS, LEO, etc.) and ground users, and there is less path loss for these links.

Future LEO satellite networks (SatNets) will provide unprecedented amount of capacity, with low latency, on a truly global scale. Software-defined satellite network concepts and machine learning will play a crucial role in unlocking the full potential of future LEO SatNets.

The promise of HAPS as a central component of the wireless network architecture consists in (1) favourable channel conditions; (2) almost geostationary positions; (3) smaller footprint compared to satellite nodes; (4) large platform; (5) even lower latency compared to satellite networks, etc. With these promises, the HAPS network will introduce *agility* to the network architecture that enables a significant network design adaptability and flexibility in addressing the variable demands of capacity and fulfilling the coverage requirements of the overall network. Particularly, HAPS as a super macro

base station (HAPS-SMBS)⁸ can provide connectivity in many applications, including high capacity, low latency, and computing requirements, especially for highly populated metropolitan areas.

On the other hand, UAVs can be used as on-demand aerial base stations (BS) and as relays in practical/emergency scenarios. UAVs can be deployed in UAV-aided relay networks to extend coverage and provide wireless connectivity for distant users without reliable direct communication links. Applying some spectrally efficient multiple access schemes such as NOMA is straightforward for air-to-ground channels rather than ground-to-ground ones.

With its bird's-eye and almost-line-of-sight view of an entire metropolitan area, a HAPS is more than a base station in the air; it is a new architecture paradigm with access, transport, and core network functionalities for integrated connectivity, computing, sensing, positioning, and navigation, towards enabling a variety of use-cases in an agile and green manner for smart societies of the future.

Fig 6: Vertical HetNets (Courtesy: K. Tekbilyik, A. R. Ekti, G. K. Kurt, A. Gorcin, and H. Yanikomeroğlu, “A holistic investigation of Terahertz propagation and channel modeling towards vertical heterogeneous networks,” IEEE Communication Magazine, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 14-20, Nov. 2020)

⁸ This concept is known under the designation High Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS) as IMT base stations (HIBS).

3.2.14 Network capacity enhancement with non-terrestrial networks and possible use cases

Enriching the IMT network with HIBS nodes will bring much needed agility to the overall network. In recent years, ITU extended the HAPS definition to HIBS (HAPS as an IMT BS). A HIBS is a new type of BS resulting in a vertical heterogeneous network with small cells, macro cells, and HIBS super macro cells. The natural next step should be to allow HIBS operations in metro (urban and suburban) areas and supporting and complementing the terrestrial network in urban areas, in addition to the legacy scenarios (i.e., rural & remote coverage). HIBS operation in metro areas in an integrated manner with small BSs and macro BSs will result in an advanced, agile, green, and sustainable wireless infrastructure in 2030s and beyond.

HIBS can also provide a third tier in urban heterogeneous networks (HetNets); i.e., HIBS-based super macro cells, in addition to macro cells and small cells. Adding a third tier to the existing two-tier urban heterogeneous networks (HetNets) provides support to the terrestrial network in the case of unpredictable and temporary excessive capacity demand. The possible deployment scenarios for HIBS to enhance capacity in urban and metro areas are as follows:

- Load sharing: urban (including sub-urban) areas covered by ground-based IMT base stations but are overloaded and/or under high-capacity demand can offload their traffic to HIBS.
- Highways with limited ground-based connectivity: HIBS can provide continuous connectivity to intelligent transportation systems (ITS) with a minimum number of handoffs.
- HIBS can cover “aerial highways” for UAV traffic.

Possible use cases for HIBS include:

Computation offloading: Users with limited computing capacity and lack of nearby ground based IMT base stations suffer from huge computing delay. However, HIBS with a large computational resource can help offloading the computing tasks from those ground users by offering direct connectivity. Further, HIBS can reduce the computing delay for delay sensitive applications such as intelligent transportation systems (ITS). In that sense, HIBS can be considered as a new layer of computing between edge and cloud computing to further reduce the delay.

One shot aggregation: Federated learning (FL) taking place through terrestrial wireless networks suffers from the limited number of participants in the vicinity of a centralized server that reduces overall learning accuracy. This limitation can be overcome by performing multi-tier FL at the cost of a longer convergence time due to multi-hop communications. However, this bottleneck can be overcome by moving the centralized server to the HIBS. Owing to the extensive ground coverage of the HIBS, moving the centralized server to the HIBS can improve the number of participants and can communicate with each of them in a single hop.

Integrated communication and sensing (ICS): Sensing with terrestrial users suffer from problems such as lack of line-of-sight (LoS) link with users and small coverage area. Whereas HIBS provides a large footprint and LoS links, it can establish reliable link with

both aerial and ground users and can be used for sensing applications such as monitoring with high resolution cameras, remote sensing with LIDAR, or IoT devices. HIBS is a promising candidate for ITS as it can sense all the signals of vehicles whether in a remote highway or downtown of a city.

Localization, positioning and navigation: Due to its lower distance to the ground users, HIBS can help for more accurate positioning. The current GPS system estimates the position of each node based on 4 MEO satellites placed at the altitude of 20,000 km. However, HIBS are placed in the stratosphere at the altitude of 20 km which means that it can be helpful for accurate positioning using techniques such as differential positioning.

Backhauling for ground based IMT BS: For terrestrial BSs, backhauling through fiber links is expensive and is impossible for some small cells. For wireless backhauling, we know that it requires a lot of bandwidth which means that we need to work in higher frequency bands for these links which are susceptible to blockages. Therefore, both wireless and fiber backhauling are hard to implement especially for dense networks. On the other hand, due to providing LoS with terrestrial BSs, HIBS is a great candidate for wireless backhauling of these BSs at higher frequency bands.

3.2.15 Self-Synthesizing Networks

To understand why the service and application offerings of telecom generations take almost a decade, the following figure illustrates the typically executed design cycle. Notably, researchers would conduct fundamental research into novel telecom principles; for the sake of argument, let us assume the invention of Massive MIMO. The invention then needs to be embedded into an operational telco system, e.g. 5G, requiring proper system designs. Once designed, it needs to be prototyped and eventually standardised. Then, it is deployed in the field, and configured for operations. Last, it is being operated and serviced.

Autonomous networking has emerged as an attractive operational technology, i.e. a technology which is being used in the deploy, configure and operations phases. For instance, in the context of Massive MIMO, autonomous algorithms may decide on the optimal transmission and receiver policies such as transmission power and choice of modulation index per degree of freedom, etc. This is typically being done by using ML/AI to tune the configuration of already invented and deployed algorithmic frameworks.

By contrast, Self-Synthesizing Networks automate the actual design process, or large parts thereof. Whilst the actual invention of engineering principles may still be done by human researchers or in combination with AI, the system design, prototyping and standards development are now largely executed by machines. Given that the two phases of systems design and standardisation take years, it is hoped that the introduction of self-synthesizing networking principles will accelerate feature development in telecoms by 5-8 years. Compute power can be scaled and design cycles of days if not minutes would be well within reach.

	Autonomous Networks	Self-Synthesising Networks*
Research	Human-Driven	Human-Driven
Systems Design	Human-Driven	Automated
Standards/Prototyping	Human-Driven	Reduced/Automated
Deploy/Configure	SON for Config	SON for Config
Operations	SON	SON

8-10 Years Acceleration of Innovation Cycle

Fig 7: Design cycle in telecoms, contrasting autonomous and self-synthesising networks

The core design principles of Self-Synthesising Networks rely on the softwarisation of the telco infrastructure through SDN and NFV. Said mechanisms rely on the ability of the network to self-reconfigure, i.e. find a new *parameterisation* for a given and *fixed set of protocols*.

The herein introduced framework of Self-Synthesising Networks, by contrast, will *automatically* translate novel algorithms (e.g. new modulation detection), protocols (e.g. new authentication protocol) and network designs (e.g. new message sequence chart) into operational software, architecture elements, standards and hardware. That will require *automated software code generation*, which ought to be framed as a sequence-to-sequence problem and design a framework that is trained end-to-end in a hierarchical, multi-task learning fashion.

To achieve self-synthesising networking capabilities, three steps need to be executed:

- i. casting novel inventions into innovation design templates;
- ii. translating these innovation design templates into machine-readable meta-language (eg UML/XML/OpenAPI3);
- iii. verifying operational consistency of the latter (e.g. through B-Language); and
- iv. subsequently translating it into operational software (e.g. C/C++/Python).

The first step casts text from, e.g. a conference or journal paper, into a more structured form; however, the output is still human-readable text. This step requires human intervention, at least initially but one can imagine this task to be taken over by semantically aware AI in the mid/long term future. It involves creating a general design template which is easier to parse for AI and thus ensures a lower error rate.

The second step requires the human-readable innovation template to be translated into a machine-readable meta-language. The translation needs to be done by suitable AI, and is discussed in the subsequent section. The output could e.g. be a mix of Unified Modeling Language (UML), Extensible Markup Language (XML) and OpenAPI.

The third step ensures that the translated meta-code is actually operationally viable. It needs to be consistent, secure and fault resistant. The field of formal verification has consolidated over recent years, and well-established tools can be used to that end. Once

verified, the fourth step requires the meta-code to be translated into an actually operational software with which modern telco applications are written. For instance, that could be C, C++, Python, YAML files, etc.

In the future, the above framework can be extended to the generation of automated standards documents. Indeed, 3GPP has moved to providing OpenAPI code in many of the recent specifications, making translation into code easier. The hardest step, however, is to translate the unstructured human-readable innovation text into a machine-readable text – this is the focus of the subsequent section.

3.2.16 Internet of Senses

In the telco context, the notion of the Internet of Senses was introduced by Ericsson in 2019⁹, which was complementing the prior art on the Internet of Skills and the Tactile Internet. Notably, the Tactile Internet (introduced by Prof Gerhard Fettweis) advocated for the use of ultra-low latency networks to accomplish challenging 1ms control loops over short distances. The Internet of Skills (introduced by Prof Mischa Dohler) advocated for the democratization of skills by enabling the transmission of physical muscle movement and touch through a low latency network spanning the entire planet.

The Internet of Senses enables full immersion and full immediacy by transmitting physical senses over the Internet. Some of these senses do not require a low latency nor an ultra-high reliability, such as the senses of touch (tactile) or smell (olfaction); indeed, a network latency of 100-200ms or even larger will not distort perception. The kinesthetic, video and audio signals, however, require very low latency and high networking fidelity; ideally, a few milliseconds ought to be achieved from any point to any other point on earth.

Illustrated in the following figure, the Internet of Senses thus needs to solve a set of important challenges in the context of 6G:

1. First, global low latency needs to be provided through the use of natively embedded edge-cloud intelligence which is able to run model-mediated prediction to circumvent the speed of light; in addition, low latency codecs and ciphers ought to be used, as well as network slicing end-to-end.
2. Second, the device and edge-robotics industry, including soft robotics, needs to be included in the design to ensure that not only the networks are ready in 2030 but also the required end-points.

⁹ “Ericsson report reveals the ‘Internet of Senses,’” Telecom Review, 12 Jan 2020; available at: <https://www.telecomreview.com/index.php/articles/reports-and-coverage/3586-ericsson-report-reveals-the-internet-of-senses>.

Fig 8: Underpinning enablers for the Internet of Senses are light compression, end-to-end slicing, and edge-cloud enabled AI

3.2.17 Quantum Technology

Quantum computing is an emerging technological paradigm that promises novel compute opportunities but is also able to compromise cybersecurity ciphers. Therefore, improved methods to mitigate such security threats are needed.

In recent research, a location-aware cryptographic system was proposed that guarantees post-quantum security. The ultimate value of a location-driven cryptosystem is to use the geographic location as an identity credential. Position-driven cryptography using lattices is efficient and lightweight, and it can be used to protect sensitive and confidential data in many critical situations that rely heavily on exchanging confidential data.

Unlike prior art, the proposed cryptosystem is the first secure and unrestricted position-based protocol that guards against any number of collusion attackers and, importantly, against quantum attacks. It has a guaranteed authentication process, solves the problems of distributing public keys by removing a public key infrastructure (PKI), offers secure telco connectivity without SIM cards, and resists location spoofing attacks.

3.2.18 Physical-Layer Security (PLS) Technologies

There is widespread consensus that security in future mobile systems will be critical. However, these systems will be highly heterogeneous and will operate under unprecedentedly diverse constraints (power, latency, computational and memory resources). Emerging technologies that pose further challenges, expanding the attack surface beyond anything witnessed - so far, need to be taken into account: the extensive introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) as well as the prospect of quantum computing. Potential controls at all layers need to be considered, and controls from the palette of physical layer security could be naturally incorporated as they are inherently adaptive. Some examples of emerging and existing PLS technologies that could be useful, include:

- Stealthy waveform and code design technologies **for enhancing resilience and robustness against active attacks at the physical layer (PHY), including the radio interface;**

- **Authentication using RF fingerprinting and hardware features.** Apart from the use of physical unclonable functions (PUFs), RF fingerprinting is promising as localization precision (e.g., with the use of mMIMO) and trustworthiness (e.g., by using multiple sources) increases.
- **The generation of symmetric keys from PHY entropy.** The generated keys from such approaches are not controlled by any party, potentially providing further privacy and security guarantees and these can be used jointly with symmetric block ciphers, e.g., AES-256 in hybrid systems.
- **Keyless transmission of confidential messages.** With the emergence of very narrow beamforming at mmWaves and sub-THz, along with visible light communications and free space optics, there is a promising use case for wiretap-coding technologies. Recent results on the secrecy performance at finite block lengths allow understanding of the trade-off between secrecy rate, error rate and privacy leakage.
- **Anomaly detection at PHY.** Recently, there have been proposals for the distributed anomaly detection by observing metrics such as transmission and reception times, energy usage and memory usage.

PLS can offer lightweight solutions for adaptive security schemes under statistical Quality of Service (QoS) delay constraints in the radio access.

3.3 IMT-2030 Vision Framework

3.3.1 Use cases trends and security considerations

For Global Inclusion to be achieved, cost efficiency is essential. Some of the functionalities required may be expensive and not required in the initial stages of deployment in developing countries, and therefore technology or technologies that maybe considered for 2030, must be flexible enough to be upgradable through software updates. As it is well known fact that some countries are just about to go from 3G to 4G, and this based on fact that return on investments on 3G is achieved before going onto 4G. Return on investment is an essential ingredient for businesses to succeed. Many of the developing countries are not thinking about 5G, so it is essential that technology or technologies selected can be upgraded by software to connect the unconnected and are affordable by developing countries as they migrate from 4G to beyond IMT-2020, either directly or via IMT-2020.

The diagram below shows that a number of different technologies will be needed to achieve global inclusion, hence the need for upgrading technologies as they are developed.

Fig 9: Technologies needed to achieve global inclusion

As we move IMT towards 2030, air interface specifications need to take on the role of further supporting security in devices. A combination of air interface and networked infrastructure with built-in security functionalities will achieve the strongest protection possible, and thereby increase user confidence and trust. Future IMT systems need to provide robust and secure solutions to address the threats to security and privacy brought by new radio technologies, new services and new deployment cases.

A system is only secure, as long as the least secure component is secure. Hence, a system should follow several security and privacy principles, including:

- i) minimizing the attack surface, authentication with adequate strength - for UE, base stations, and network nodes
- ii) enforcing least privilege (e.g. a UE should not be able to send control messages beyond a restricted network zone)

- iii) separation of duties (e.g. entities or components should be separated based on data sensitivity)
- iv) protection of sensitive data in storage, transit and display
- v) enforce minimal trust (e.g. limit trust of third-party services);
- vi) fail securely and gracefully (e.g. failure to authenticate should not allow a malicious user to gain sensitive information to further the attack)
- vii) apply defence in depth (e.g. use multiple layers of validation, different security auditing, and logging mechanism)
- vii) apply security and privacy by default and simplicity, KISS principle:
 - secure by design, development, and deployment
 - avoid security by obscurity (e.g., there should be sufficient security without hiding protocol or encryption algorithms).

It is expected that in year 2030 and beyond, sensing and advanced AI will enable a much fuller context awareness, moving from “connecting things” to “connected intelligence”. In its turn, context awareness can drive the Quality of Security (QoSec) experienced by users and enable the adaptation of security controls. These are especially pertinent for constrained wireless systems, such as Internet of things (IoT), with ultra-low latencies and massive connectivity. The roadmap for the incorporation of context awareness into wireless security encompasses the following ideas:

- harvesting context through sensing
- distilling security-relevant context through semantic compression
- context-aware risk assessment, through the semantic fusion of the distilled context with network and application layer information
- developing security controls that can adapt to context.

Examples of these domain areas might include how physical-layer security (PLS) can offer lightweight solutions for adaptive security schemes under statistical Quality of Service (QoS) delay constraints in the radio access. Additionally, techniques for lightweight distributed anomaly detection in constrained wireless sensor networks, based on results from signal processing and deep-learning-enabled indoor localization, can be applied to allow early authentication in multi-factor authentication protocols. Overall, emerging techniques using context gathered from the radio network can significantly enhance the experienced Quality of Security.

3.3.2 Use case 1: Enhanced human-centric communication

The continuous evolution of enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) for human-centric communication use cases to enable extremely immersive experience and multi-sensory interactions in XR applications and remote telepresence. These use cases will come with much higher requirement in peak data rate, user experienced data rate, low end-to-end latency, and large system capacity in terms of throughput and number of access. It will enable a range of use cases in entertainment, education, manufacturing and navigation,

transforming the way people live, learn, work, and travel. Both indoor and outdoor cases are needed, where seamless user experience in the target activity areas are to be guaranteed. In the extreme case, seamless experience shall be maintained along the end-to-end route of activities with both indoor and outdoor high mobility case. User experienced data rate in remote areas and during trips on aeroplanes or ships shall be maintained to support ubiquitous high quality connections.

Some examples include:

- 360 degree full-view extremely immersive XR
- Interactive haptic and multi-sensory communications for teleoperation
- Glass-free 3D and holographic display integrated with XR
- Mobile broadband for trips on aero planes or ships.

3.3.3 Use case 2: Network for Sensing / Sensing as a service

Network for sensing creates a new type of usage scenario beyond communication that covers a range of use cases such as localization for device-based or even device-free targets, imaging, environment reconstruction and monitoring, gesture and activity recognition. The sensing usage scenario adds new performance dimensions to the IMT such as detection probability, sensing resolution and accuracy in range, velocity, and angles, the requirements of which varies from applications to applications. For localization and reconstruction applications in the future, high sensing accuracy and resolution are both demanded while for imaging cases, ultra-high resolution is the key. And for gesture and activity recognition, detection probability becomes the top priority.

Some examples include:

- Ultra-high accuracy positioning, localization, and tracking
- Simultaneous imaging, mapping and localization, 4D map
- Augmented human sense
- Gesture and Activity recognition
- Environmental monitoring.

3.3.4 Use case 3: Network for AI / AI as a Service

Intelligence is provided as native service from the mobile communication system, which could be used by the network itself for resource scheduling, network operation and management purpose. Moreover, it could be provided to end users via exposed network capabilities.

This use case targets to connect the distributed intelligent agents and connect them intelligently to proliferate large-scale deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) in all sectors of society. Spectral efficient, high-capacity and low latency transmission for distributed learning, including data and/or model parameter exchange among a large number of

intelligent agents, is expected for real-time AI. Native trustworthiness with the support of native security and local data privacy is a key aspect for this usage scenario to take off.

Some examples include:

- AI-enhanced network performance
- AI-enhanced Network Operation
- Aiaas for data management
- Aiaas for distributed learning and inferencing.

3.3.5 New use cases trends for public safety networks and mobile health

The use cases for IMT 2030 require ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), especially for applications that involve critical decision making. One example is the use case regarding public safety and health networks, which has been identified as an important IMT 2030 use case. Moving forward from current networks, the network architecture for public safety will evolve to amalgamate different technologies with networks such as artificial intelligence (AI)-based networks. The network architecture for public safety networks may be centralised or decentralised, based on the deployment scenario. Mobile edge computing (MEC) can play a key role in providing an intelligent solution for public safety networks, where the decision making needs to be quick and efficient. AI and MEC will drive the advancement towards future critical networks, especially in scenarios where network resilience needs to be ensured for sustainability of networks. This highlights the necessity for designing new architecture for public safety networks. Moreover, for applications involving high computation an edge mesh may be required to fulfil the computation requirements. In a nutshell, the next generation networks for public safety will be aided by the aforementioned technologies and will involve enhanced intelligence for ensuring quick decision making.

Use case: Connected Ambulances

Telemedicine and Telehealth allows remote transmission and reception of health-related data for various purposes such as health monitoring, early clinical decision making and, in some cases, remote diagnosis. The concept of IMT-2020-enabled connected ambulances is close to become a reality where doctors or physicians will have access to in-ambulance data of patients as soon as the paramedics reach the scene of emergency. In the healthcare industry, one of the biggest challenges has always been limited resources and time is of great essence in clinical decision making. The earlier and more accurate the diagnosis, the less the damage to the patient leading to efficient consumption of medical resources. The in-ambulance data that is collected and transmitted in a connected ambulance contains Electrocardiogram (ECG) data as well. This is a type of time series data that can help the doctors to classify and detect different types of cardiovascular diseases (CVD).

Though, in a connected ambulance, a doctor has direct access to patient's ECG it still takes time for the doctors to correctly read the ECG and identify any anomalies. These are then further classified into CVDs. Also, for connected ambulances to be a success, there will always be a need for a doctor to be connected remotely. An AI-based decision-making system for classification and prediction of CVDs using ECG data can be an

efficient way of helping doctors in reducing time for clinical decision making. Furthermore, such system can evolve into a highly accurate diagnostic tool for CVDs where doctors will only need to spend a few moments of their time to verify the results in case of false positives or false negatives. ECG data is produced in massive amounts on daily basis and having such huge sets of data can eventually help in creating a mature AI-based diagnostic tool.

Furthermore, with Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), processing the data in an ultrafast and ultra-reliable fashion will no longer be a problem. A simple architecture of this idea would include the following steps:

- Collection of ECG data.
- Transmission of ECG data to the nearest MEC platform.
- Processing the data and then classification of anomalies and CVD detection, which will take place in the MEC platform.
- Transmission by the MEC platform of the classification and CVD detection results to the doctors.

3.3.6 Usage Scenarios

To expand, complement and refine the usage scenarios considered in 5G in order to incorporate the notions of immersion, digitization and intelligence, the following usage scenarios can be considered.

Usage Scenario 1: Backhaul/fronthaul global connectivity

Due to the forecasted exponential data rate increase and the requirement for global inclusion, mobile access networks in the forthcoming beyond 5G networks are going to emigrate towards heterogeneous cell structures, dominated by the backhaul/fronthaul connectivity scenario. The high potential of mmWave spectrum and/or the beyond 100 GHz spectrum is

expected to be exploited in order to accommodate, through the higher offered bandwidth, the ever-increasing data-rate demands of mobile users.

In terms of deployment targeting global inclusion and heterogeneous connectivity, the following scenarios are envisioned:

- Long-range LOS rooftop point-to-point backhauling
- Street-level point-to-point and point-to-multipoint backhaul/fronthaul
- Long range ('fiber-extender') rural coverage

Usage scenario 2: Immersive connectivity

The requirement for dynamic reconfiguration in obstructed/NLOS scenarios, in order to track slowly moving users, introduces several challenges wrt transceivers adaptation, channel estimation, localization and resources management. Examples of advanced NLOS connectivity include immersive communications, materialized by means of the internet of senses, where integrated communications and sensing usage scenarios are foreseen.

Immersive connectivity will enable Augmented/Virtual/Mixed Reality application empowered by holographic communication technologies and Digital Twinning capabilities.

In terms of deployment targeting immersive connectivity, the following scenarios are envisioned:

- Advanced NLOS immersive connectivity empower by reconfigurable intelligent surfaces
- Data kiosk /data shower
- Extreme data rate and ultra low latency for Mixed Reality and Digital Twinning

Usage scenario 3: Intelligent connectivity in dynamic network topology

Drones in future networks are seen as a way to extend the notion of coverage to that of intelligent connectivity. They can be essential in emergency cases when backhaul/fronthaul nodes stop operating due to malfunctioning or physical disaster. Due to the failure of a remote radio head, a drone can be deployed with attached remote radio head to serve the affected users.

Vehicles can be equipped with transceivers for reliable fast communication of road/traffic conditions to preceding cars (vehicle-to-vehicle - V2V). Moreover, traffic lights may dispatch critical information to vehicles approaching (vehicle-to-everything -V2X).

Intelligent connectivity in dynamic network topologies will largely depend on the integration of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning principles and the extend to which AI-native communications vision could be materialized.

In terms of deployment of intelligent connectivity in dynamic network topologies, the following scenarios are envisioned:

- Dynamic front/backhaul connectivity for mobile 5G access nodes and repeaters
- V2V and V2X connectivity

Usage scenario 4: Internet of Senses

The integration of sensors/actuators is expected to play a decisive role in realizing the vision of digitization and programmability of the physical world, the real time interaction between virtual and physical entities and the joint design of communication and sensing systems. The latter would require the seamless incorporation of multiple senses (haptic, smell, taste etc) and the efficient design of multidimensional sensing approaches. Ultra-high precision, resolution, synchronization and analysis of heterogeneous data signal is of paramount importance.

In terms of deployment of the internet of senses, the following scenarios are envisioned:

- Multi-dimensional sensing
- ‘Sixth sense’ communications

Fig 10: Usage scenarios evolution from IMT 2020 to IMT 2030: 4 new usage scenarios envisioned, namely Global Connectivity, Immersive Connectivity, Intelligent Connectivity and Internet of Senses

3.3.7 Key capabilities

In addition to the key capabilities already included in the IMT-2030 framework, carried over from IMT-2020, the new technological challenges and associated enabling technologies require the introduction of new capabilities, tailored to capture performance indicators suitable for the newly identified usage scenarios. The most critical key capabilities are described in the following paragraphs.

Energy efficiency

Assessing performance metrics unit per energy unit required (in bits/Joule) is a key design efficiency indicator for both the network and the user equipment sides.

Other capabilities may be also required for IMT-2030, which are mainly associated with qualitative or 'soft' attributes tightly connected to the key visionary pillars of immersion, programmability and intelligence. These capabilities include:

Sensing resolution

Sensing accuracy, adaptability, agility and reliability are decisive parameters for the efficient integration of sensing into future communication systems and networks [in max acceptable sensing error margin].

Localization accuracy

Localization accuracy will significantly impact the implementation of immersion, digital twinning and native intelligence [in meters].

Trustworthiness

The ability to provide advanced system and service resilience, reliability, availability, confidentiality, privacy and safety.

3.4 Technical Feasibility of IMT in bands above 100 GHz**3.4.1 Directional antennas and pencil beamforming in the (sub)THz regime**

The limited transmission power of transceivers in frequencies above 100 GHz, combined with the high propagation losses at these frequencies (resulting mostly from the small effective area of antennas, when operating within the molecular absorption free bands of the spectrum above 100 GHz), require the utilization of high-gain directional antennas and pencil beamforming techniques at the transmitter and the receiver of a communication link. Usually, in the literature, such antennas are assumed to be static, and the problem is mostly in determining the correct direction and the optimal antenna (array) pattern in order to maximize the antenna/beamforming gain. However, sustaining perfectly aligned transmitter and receiver antennas and /or optimal antenna (array) patterns in practical scenarios is not always feasible, due to various factors, such as thermal expansion, dynamic wind loads, weak earthquakes and other physical phenomena causing vibrations of the transceivers antennas. These phenomena result in -often severe- beam misalignment. Moreover, estimation errors in the angle of arrival or angle of departure as well as hardware imperfections in the antenna array, which include array perturbation and mutual coupling, and, most importantly, mobility in various random trajectories, may cause stochastic tracking estimation errors. Robust beamforming and tracking techniques, capable of supporting adaptation to the particularities of challenging usage scenarios, are therefore key performance factors.

In addition to high propagation losses, THz signals can be obstructed (i.e., absorbed, reflected or diffracted) by different types of obstacles (e.g. people, furniture, walls,

windows etc). These obstructing obstacles can create a shadow area which might (partially) block the receiver antenna effective area. Moreover, the obstacle itself might reflect and/or absorb the signal. As much as directionality and pencil beamforming are necessary to ensure connectivity reliability in the above 100 GHz regime, they may, at the same time, intensify the blockage challenges. Incorporating Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) is a way to overcome blockage and reduce blocking probability.

3.4.2 Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in the (sub)THz regime

One of the major challenges of operating in above 100 GHz band is the obstructed propagation environment due to high propagation loss and blockage. RISs have been explored as a potential solution towards sustaining non line-of-sight communication, introduce reconfigurability and programmability of the wireless propagation channel and ensuring communication at higher frequency with mobile objects. RISs comprise of multiple elements ('unit cells') and, by tuning their phase shifts, it is possible to control the propagation direction of impinging electromagnetic waves. RISs can reflect the waves in a particular direction and can impact the phase of the reflected wave. RISs have been explored for both indoor and outdoor network environments and the initial prototypes have demonstrated their potential in aiding communication at high frequency bands.

RISs are also considered as a key enabler for Terahertz communications, though there are multiple challenges that need to be addressed before RISs are adopted. Ensuring smooth RIS operation supporting reconfigurability, where mobile users are involved, requires a control system architecture that empowers tunable / programmable RIS operation, e.g. with respect to the desired beam steering and beamforming. Moreover, the controller design needs to take the contextual information into consideration, to reduce the vulnerability due to blockages and sustain the communication for mobile users. Gathering the contextual information can lead to high computational overhead and delays in the controller mechanism. Another challenge is the channel estimation as multiple channels might be involved. In a nutshell, RISs are considered as a promising technology for above 100 GHz network operation but also pose several design and optimization challenges.

3.4.3 Beam-tracking

While the use of directional antennas can potentially help mitigate high path loss and blockage challenges in frequencies above 100 GHz, the need for careful beam alignment becomes crucial, especially when the user moves. To ensure a reliable directional link, beam-tracking may be performed, and several parameters must be taken into account, such as the type of user's motion, the location of the access point, the geometry of the area, the beam width, etc. The directional link reliability is determined by two main parameter categories, related to the trajectory tracking resolution and the angular resolution¹⁰. The trajectory tracking resolution contains the parameters that affect the prediction of the tracking algorithms, and the angular resolution contains the parameters that affect successful estimation in each timeslot. Beam-tracking consists in an

¹⁰ G. Stratidakis, S. Droulias, and A. Alexiou. "A beam-tracking framework for THz networks." *Frontiers in Communications and Networks* 3 (2022): 965336 (<https://doi.org/10.3389/frcmn.2022.965336>)

initialization phase, including a hierarchical search, ranging and location estimation steps and in a tracking phase, including location prediction, direction estimation and regular refinement steps. Efficient beam-tracking will need to address the challenges of both parameter categories, in order to achieve an optimal trade-off between high tracking reliability and low pilot overhead. Location estimation and prediction based on multiple Access Points cooperation may further improve this trade-off.

Fig 11: Beam tracking

3.4.4 Massive MIMO

The extremely short wavelengths at frequencies above 100 GHz offer the possibility of implementation of (2- and 3-dimensional) antenna array structures within a small size. Massive MIMO (massive-element antenna array) systems enable the implementation of high-gain pencil beamforming (to account for severe path loss). Moreover, massive MIMO systems can offer multiple beams/ massive spatial Degrees of Freedom and therefore achieve impressive spectral efficiency gains by exploiting extreme spatial resolution (Space Division Multiple Access) and spatial multiplexing gains.

Extreme densification in IMT systems towards 2030 operating in frequencies above 100 GHz, both in terms of device density and in terms of supporting network elements, combined with ultra-high bandwidths and massive multi beam MIMO techniques, will help maximize user throughput and network capacity per unit area, in order to support new disruptive services and applications, such as immersive communications.

Massive multi-beam steering at frequencies above 100 GHz not only provides flexibility and efficiency in ultra-dense IMT systems but also enables reconfigurability and self-healing capabilities, necessary to efficiently address blockage, misalignment, location estimation and tracking challenges. Dynamic, intelligent management of multi-beam IMT system resources (such as frequency, power, modulation, available paths, etc.) is key for the fully programmable radio systems envisioned towards 2030 and beyond.

3.4.5 RIS-aided beamforming

In a conventional Line-of-Sight link, the beam travels from the transmitter directly to the receiver with increasing width –due to free-space propagation– and therefore with decreasing power density, which can be further reduced by possible atmospheric

absorption and scattering. For a certain emitted beam power, the narrower the beam-width at the receiver, the higher the power density and the more the power that can be received. However, when an intermediate re-radiating element, such as a RIS, comes into play, this intuitive picture can change entirely. The reason is that the RIS is essentially a secondary antenna; it is driven by the incident field from the transmitter and is re-emitting a secondary beam (towards the receiver), the propagation characteristics of which depend on both the incident power density on the RIS and the illuminated area.

The optimization of the trade-off between the RIS size, the transmitter beam-width and power density can provide a clear quantitative assessment of the efficiency of a RIS-aided beamforming link¹¹. For relatively low gain, the transmitter beam illuminates the entire RIS and, therefore, the footprint of the secondary beam does not depend on the transmitter beam width but is rather determined by the actual area of the RIS (the effective aperture of the RIS is determined by the finite area of the RIS); we refer to this case as finite RIS regime. On the other hand, for relatively high gain, the transmitter beam illuminates only a portion of the RIS and, therefore, the width of the secondary beam on the RIS is defined entirely by the transmitter beam footprint, i.e., the actual RIS size does not matter (the effective aperture of the RIS is determined by the transmitter beam footprint); in this case the transmitter beam sees an effectively infinite RIS and we refer to this case as infinite RIS regime.

Fig 12: Finite vs Infinite RIS regimes

When the entire transmitter beam is captured by the RIS (infinite RIS regime) the RIS-aided beamforming link can be easily modeled by treating the RIS as a continuous surface (instead of considering the discrete nature of the RIS as an array of unit cells). In the infinite RIS regime, for high transmitter gain the pathloss increases with increasing distance between the RIS and the receiver. For low transmitter gain, the received power is independent of the distance between the RIS and the receiver, since the beam propagation is in the near-field, the peak power of the beam is practically constant. The

¹¹ G. Stratidakis, S. Droulias and A. Alexiou, "Analytical Performance Assessment of Beamforming Efficiency in Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Aided Links," in IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 115922-115931, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3105477.

necessary transmitter gain to reach the maximum received power marks the transition from near-field to far-field regimes.

Fig 13: Near-field vs Far-field RIS regimes

This analytical framework assessing the trade-off between the RIS size, the transmitter beam-width and power density offers a useful RIS design, optimization and programmability tool.

3.4.6 Large Intelligent Surfaces and Beam Focusing

The deployment of Large Intelligent Surfaces (LIS), which can be considered as extremely large ‘reconfigurable’ antenna arrays, especially in frequencies above 100 GHz, indicates that future IMT systems are likely to operate in the radiating near-field region¹², as opposed to the traditional far-field operation of current radio technologies. While in the far-field electromagnetic wavefronts can be approximated as planar, in the radiating near-field the spherical wavefront shape can be exploited to provide beam focusing, i.e. focusing of signals on a specific point/direction. Beam focusing in frequency bands above 100 GHz is a promising enabler for multi-user MIMO communications and integrated communications and localization/sensing usage scenarios, as it allows for dynamic interference management/shaping and capacity-achieving multi-user communications. Nevertheless, in order to exploit the potential of LIS and their Beam Focusing capabilities, a number of design challenges associated with near-field channel modeling, channel estimation, robustness and hardware constraints need to be carefully addressed.

¹² Parisa Ramezani, Emil Björnson, “Near-Field Beamforming and Multiplexing Using Extremely Large Aperture Arrays”, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.03082>

Fig 14: Beam steering vs beam focusing

3.4.7 Wavefront Engineering

Owing to its large surface and the multitude of unit cells, the RIS can be exploited to perform advanced wavefront engineering, involving phase shifts beyond the simple linear RIS phase gradient that is required to perform conventional beam steering. With judicious design, the RIS can transform the incident beam into a nontrivial reflected beam that is able to address the challenges of high frequencies more efficiently than conventional beam forming. Wavefront engineering offers new capabilities and features, such as flexible control of channel gain with beams, opening up new possibilities for joint communication and sensing.

Fig 15: Wavefront engineering

The capability to flexibly engineer the wavefront, taking into consideration environmental parameters and usage scenario characteristics, introduces novel capabilities, where communication nodes can be employed to 'read' the shape of surrounding obstacles, map the environment, detect the presence of objects, focus power, localize, track mobility and navigate.

Extending the beamforming capabilities of RISs to advanced wavefront engineering will enable precise beam control for a plethora of applications. As mentioned in the previous section, to further boost the link performance, beam focusing capabilities enable energy efficient communications and new codebooks for localization and sensing applications. Moreover, non-diffracting beams can be employed to mitigate the increased propagation attenuation. To counteract blockage, bending beams can be used, that is, beams that are able to propagate along a curved trajectory, and self-healing beams, that is, beams that are able to reconstruct after being interrupted by a small blocker.

4. Conclusion & Next Steps

The exploration of the IMT2030 framework reveals a promising future, where the evolution of wireless communications, marked by unprecedented speed, reliability, and transformative applications will be realised. The integration of AI and edge computing stands out as key enablers, enhancing the efficiency and responsiveness of IMT2030 networks. Despite the potential, challenges such as spectrum allocation, security concerns, and global standardisation require focused attention for the successful deployment and realisation of IMT2030's full potential. As we approach the year 2030, it is imperative for industry stakeholders, policymakers, and innovators to collaborate on addressing these challenges, ensuring a seamless transition to IMT2030 and reaping the benefits of a connected world that transcends current limitations. This WWRF Outlook publication supports and stresses the importance of continued research, development, and global collaboration to harness the transformative power of IMT2030 for the benefit of global connectivity, economic growth, and societal advancement.

The WWRF Vision group plans to closely follow the IMT-2030 activities within WP5D and provide recommendations and inputs, where possible and when needed.

5. List of Figures

Fig 1: ITU timeline for IMT-2030	5
Fig 2: Key topics towards IMT vision 2030 AND Beyond.....	6
Fig 3: IMT-2030 Usage Scenarios.....	7
Fig 4: IMT-2030 Capabilities	7
Fig 5: Use cases and wireless access scenarios for systems beyond IMT-2020 (source www.ict-ariadne.eu)	22
Fig 6: Vertical HetNets (Courtesy: K. Tekbiyik, A. R. Ekti, G. K. Kurt, A. Gorcin, and H. Yanikomeroglu, "A holistic investigation of Terahertz propagation and channel modeling towards vertical heterogeneous networks," IEEE Communication Magazine, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 14-20, Nov. 2020)	24
Fig 7: Design cycle in telecoms, contrasting autonomous and self-synthesising networks	27
Fig 8: Underpinning enablers for the Internet of Senses are light compression, end-to-end slicing, and edge-cloud enabled AI	29
Fig 9: Technologies needed to achieve global inclusion.....	31
Fig 10: Usage scenarios evolution from IMT 2020 to IMT 2030: 4 new usage scenarios envisioned, namely Global Connectivity, Immersive Connectivity, Intelligent Connectivity and Internet of Senses.....	37
Fig 11: Beam tracking	40
Fig 12: Finite vs Infinite RIS regimes.....	41
Fig 13: Near-field vs Far-field RIS regimes	42
Fig 14: Beam steering vs beam focusing	43
Fig 15: Wavefront engineering	43

6. List of References

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7. List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation/Acronym	Explanation
AI / ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
CP-CDMA	Cyclic Prefix-Code Division Multiple Access
CVD	Cardio-Vasculair Diseases
DAM	Direct Antenna Modulation
ECG	Electrocardiogram
FSS	Frequency Selective Surfaces
ISM	Intelligent Spectrum Management
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
KPIs	key-performance-indicators
LIS	Large Intelligent Surfaces
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
NLOS	Non-Line of Sight
NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
OAM	Orbital Angular Momentum
QoS	Quality of Service
PDNR	Preliminary Draft New Report
RSMA	Rate-Splitting Multiple Access
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
SCMA	Sparse Code Multiple Access
SDGs)	Sustainability Development Goals
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
WWRF	Wireless World Research Forum

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